

QUICK PHOTO GUIDE TO THE SOUTH AFRICAN *GASTERACANTHA* SPECIES

Compiled by Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman

For more information and credits for photographs used see:

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A. S., HADDAD, C. R., FOORD, S. H., LOTZ, L. N. & WEBB, P. (2022e). *The Araneidae of South Africa*. Version 2: part 2 (E-Ne). South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 64 pp. <https://doi:10.5281/zenodo.6619195>

1. *Gasteracantha falcicornis* Butler, 1873

2. *Gasteracantha milvoides* Butler, 1873

3. *Gasteracantha sanguinolenta* C. L. Koch, 184

4. *Gasteracantha versicolor* (Walckenaer, 1842)

KEY TO THE AFRICAN GASTERCANTHA SPECIES -FEMALE (BENOIT, 1962)

1. Spines 2 excessively long, folded backward and extending far beyond the posterior edge of the body.....2
 - Spines 2 spread laterally or very slightly curved backward.....3
2. Spines 2 folded backward from the base; the distal quarter is subparallel or curved inward. Spines 3 very elongated and generally a little shorter than Spines 2. Found in West Africa and Central Africa.....**G. curvispina**
- Spines 2 curved backward in a broad, regular arc of about one-quarter of a circle. Spines 3 much shorter than Spines 2, normally not exceeding a third of their length. Found in Southern and Eastern Africa**G. falcicornis**
3. Spines 2 elongated, longer than the carapace length, spread laterally and slightly curved. Epigyne with a simple lobe on the lower edge (no tooth), not incised at the top. Found in Southern and Eastern Africa**G. milvoides**
- Spines 2 shorter than the carapace length.....4
4. Spines 2 at least twice as long as the distance between sigilla 5-6**G. versicolor**
- Spines 2 as long or barely longer than the distance between sigilla 5-6, and significantly thickened at the base**G. sanguinolenta**

Gasteracantha curvispina